

Smart Computers - Recent Technology Trends in Computer Technology

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Abstract: *Current user interfaces are not very "smart" in that computers dumbly do what the user explicitly commands it to do via buttons or menus. As computers become more capable and applications become complicated, more "smart" user interfaces are desired. We are exploring possible "smart" user interfaces in the domain of pen-based computing and interactive 3D graphics. The idea is to allow the user to intuitively express his/her intention by combining sketching and direct manipulation and have the computer take appropriate actions without explicit commands. This talk consists of many live demonstrations to illustrate the idea of interactive "smart" interfaces. I plan to show 2D geometric drawing programs, electronic whiteboard systems, sketch-based 3D modeling, automatic zooming, clothing manipulation interfaces, and other interesting systems*

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I. INTRODUCTION

Following the well-known concepts of computerization and informatization, an emerging era of cyberization, which is considered as a reformation of the present physical, social, and mental worlds, has become a hotly discussed trend in the new cyber world. Cyberization refers to using communication and computer technologies to interconnect computers and various electronic terminal devices distributed in different locations. It allows users to share software, hardware and data resources according to certain network protocols. Cyberization has greatly improved the practical utility of computers and has been widely applied in transportation, finance, business management, education, telecommunications, commerce, and so on in our daily life (Raza et al., 2015).

During the cyberization process, a large number of real things will conjugatively map to various kinds and levels of cyber existence in cyber world. It is said that cyberization has already taken place in a variety of fields along with the development of several emerging computing paradigms and information communication technologies, such as ubiquitous/pervasive computing, social computing and networking, and wearable technologies, etc. Specifically, with the rapid growth of the Internet of Things and cognitive cyber-physical systems, more and more digital things, or cyber entities, are engaged or generated in the integrated cyber world. Emerging technologies in smart environments, such as smart computing and smart objects, become very significant, promising, and enabling issues in cyberization, to enhance the efficiency of sensing, processing, and communication in the conjugations of physical, social, and mental worlds. Accordingly, cyber technology is playing an important role in developing effective methods of resource management, data acquisition, and pattern recognition across cyber-related systems and applications. All these provide us with opportunities to explore smart computing methodologies and computational intelligence algorithms to facilitate the cyberization process in the cyber world.

This special issue aims to report high-quality research on recent progress in the various areas related to Smart Computing and Cyber Technology for Cyberization. Our goal is to shed light on the multiple aspects involved in cyberization, encompassing algorithms, techniques, applications, enabling technologies, and platforms, besides security issues. A total of 36 papers were submitted from all over the world. After a careful review process performed by reviewers selected by the Guest Editors, 18 papers were accepted addressing subjects that were classified in the following categories: (i) infrastructure and platforms for intelligent systems, (ii) smart sensors and ad-hoc wireless networks, (iii) behavior and influence analytics in social computing, (iv) machine learning and intelligent applications,

and (v) privacy and security in smart computing. The detailed contributions of each paper are summarized in the next section.

1.1 Infrastructure and Platforms for Intelligent Systems

An important component in the cyberization process is the computational intelligence techniques and methods that are at the core of cyber world enabling processes. Recently there has been a tremendous advance in the fields of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI). However, much of this advance has focused on algorithms and their applications. Much less emphasis has been given to the underlying infrastructure of these intelligent systems. Currently, the mainstream in ML/AI consists of work being done individually by experts in the field, following ad-hoc processes that make collaboration difficult, and with little support from abstractions and tooling to facilitate the deployment of intelligent systems at scale. Ultimately, this is mainly due to a delay in infrastructure evolution, which has so far been far outweighed by innovation in machine learning techniques. One can say that the systems and tools that helped usher in the present era of hands-on machine learning are not suitable to feed future generations of the intelligent applications they have generated. Therefore, it is important to advance not only the algorithms but also the infrastructure and computing platforms that allow the effective and efficient execution of such algorithms.

In the context of ubiquitous/pervasive intelligent systems and cyber-physical systems (CPSs), cloud computing has been the most prevailing model and platform for data processing and storage. Because of the richness of resources typical of cloud platforms, cloud-based CPSs, and cloud-assisted IoT extend and augment the computing capacity of CPSs to conduct resource-hungry applications. The Cloud computing model is keen to use centralized shared resources and addresses the raising popularity of smart apps by integrating exclusive resources and the data obtained from them (An *et al.*, 2016).

In order to provide the physical resources dynamically, virtualized technology is extensively used for resource management in the cloud platforms, which provides an effective way to improve the resource efficiency of the cloud-based CPSs. Running applications on virtual machines (VMs) makes it possible for high resource utilization and low energy consumption (Wu *et al.*, 2016). Although virtualization techniques have been extensively studied in the cloud computing field, there are still several open issues involved in the allocation and migration of VMs to meet the quality of service (QoS) demands of cloud-based CPSs. A key challenge involves considering the benefits of migrating VMs to provide better QoS to the user while taking into account migration costs, for example in terms of transmission delays. In addition, energy consumption in cloud-based systems is also an increasingly relevant challenge to consider. To meet the growing demand for new scenarios such as CPSs and IoT, the capabilities of cloud data centers have grown steadily. Such growth results in the increasing power consumption of these data centers. In times of energy crisis and with the growing demand for greener and more sustainable technology solutions, reducing energy consumption in data centers has become a key goal. The authors in the paper “*A QoS-Aware Virtual Machine Scheduling Method for Energy Conservation in Cloud-based Cyber-Physical Systems*” aim to tackle the aforementioned challenges. Their goal is to find an optimal VM scheduling strategy in cloud-based CPSs with QoS enhancement. For such, they propose a QoS-aware VM scheduling method for energy conservation, named QVMS. By offloading several applications to other physical machines (PMs), the workloads on some under-load physical servers are migrated out, and these servers could be set to idle mode for energy saving. In the paper, they first define some basic concepts and present the system model. Then, they formalize the objective function and present the constraints assumed to model the solution. Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-III) is adopted to find the optimal VM scheduling strategies and achieve the goal of QoS enhancement including energy consumption, downtime, and resource utilization. Besides, SAW (Simple Additive Weighting) and MCDM (Multiple Criteria Decision Making) are adopted to select the most optimal scheduling strategy. They performed extensive experimental evaluations to verify the effectiveness of their proposed VM scheduling method them (An *et al.*, 2016).

However, despite the popularity of cloud computing as a backend of intelligent ubiquitous systems and CPSs, newly emerging applications and information technologies are very demanding when it comes to latency and bandwidth. Their requirements for the optimized transport network and processing of data performed as close to the end devices as possible are also rapidly increasing (J, Jeba et al., 2023). Some of the drawbacks of cloud platforms such as latency and jitter effects, distance to the server, data security and privacy, and support of mobility cannot be solved by the adoption

of the hyper-scale cloud computing technology. To overcome some of such limitations, the Edge Computing paradigm has recently emerged as a solution for delivering data and real-time data processing closer to the data source. The combination of Edge Computing with ML/AI gave rise to a new paradigm known as Edge intelligence (EI). EI comprises edge computing that is supported by machine learning algorithms and advanced networking abilities. The implication is that a number of information technology and operational technology industries are gravitating to the edge of the network. The result is that issues such as cybersecurity, self-learning, real-time networks, and tailored connectivity can all be adequately dealt with. In their previous work, the authors of the paper “*A Lightweight and Cost Effective Edge Intelligence Architecture based on Containerization Technology*” proposed the idea to build and integrate Docker containers within the edge and pinpoint the Edge Intelligence’s potential in the vertical-specific scenarios of use. Their current study, included in this Special Issue, extends this idea further and focuses on the utilization of Docker technology in the recognition of human activity.

They expect their presented architecture to provide significantly shorter delays in communication and decision-making as well as decrease the costs related to these processes thanks to the adoption of a lightweight and economical platform. Since the proposed architecture is using ML algorithms and eliminating any unnecessary communication with the cloud, it is able to provide more effective and quick decision-making. Unwanted delays are decreased thanks to avoiding unreasonable roundtrips. As another contribution of their proposal, decreased use of public-wide area networks along with the adoption of local algorithms and caching result in less costly communication. They also promote a good balance of applications, networks and user requests among the edge and core infrastructure. Finally, the proposed computing model can utilize decisions related to the pre-processed data and adopt alarms traded between several edge devices (Abbasi, et al., 2007).

Also leveraging the computational resources at the edge of the network, the paper “*LW-CoEdge: A lightweight virtualization model and collaboration process for Edge Computing*” proposes a novel distributed and lightweight virtualization model targeting the edge tier. Besides a novel virtualization model tailored to the edge tier and meeting the specific requirements of IoT applications, their proposal encompasses a set of heuristic algorithms along with a P2P collaboration process to operate upon the virtualization model. The algorithms perform (i) a distributed resource management process, and (ii) data sharing among neighboring virtual nodes (VNs, deployed at edge nodes). The distributed resource management process provides each edge node with decision-making capability, engaging neighboring edge nodes to allocate or provision on-demand VNs. Thus, distributed resource management improves system performance, serving more requests and handling edge node geographical distribution. Meanwhile, data sharing reduces the data transmissions between end devices and edge nodes, saving energy and reducing data traffic for IoT-edge infrastructures (Gao et al., 2014).

Among the existing CPSs, manufacturing, and enterprise applications are one of the major drivers of advanced and intelligent networked systems following the trend of Industry 4.0. Massive data are generated in a distributed fashion and cross-domain data need to be shared and analyzed in an efficient manner to realize effective supply chain management. Therefore, master data management (MDM) that manages how data are stored in a distributed system plays a critical role in enterprise data warehousing and analyses. The paper “*Master Data Management for Manufacturing Big Data: A Method of Evaluation for Data Network*” proposes a multi-layer master data management architecture and investigates the use of Set Pair Analysis (SAP) to model the distributed data network. The proposed methodology is validated using aviation enterprise data and has demonstrated the ability to support timely updates, responses, and distribution of data at each stage of the supply chain (Khan et al., 2012).

II. METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Smart Sensors and Ad-Hoc Wireless Networks

CPSs rely on a strong synergy between computational and physical components. A CPS is the integration of abstract computations and physical processes where sensors, actuators, and embedded devices are networked to sense, monitor, and control the physical world. Therefore, smart sensors and wireless sensor networks are major components of CPSs. Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are composed of tiny devices equipped with sensing, processing, storage, and wireless communication capabilities. Each node of the network can typically have several sensing units, able to perform measurements of physical variables, such as temperature, luminosity, humidity, and vibration, thus being the main

components to create a perception of the physical world. WSN nodes operate collaboratively, extracting environmental data, performing the same (often) simple processing, and then transmitting them to external systems, via sink nodes, to be analyzed and further processed.

Sensor nodes are severely constrained regarding memory, energy, and processing capabilities. Therefore, several approaches have been proposed to reduce the energy consumption of these nodes in order to extend the overall lifetime of the system. Since radio communication is the dominant factor of energy consumption in most WSNs (except for the hungry devices of multimedia sensor networks), an effective approach is the reduction of data transmission between the sink and the sensing nodes. One of the most commonly used techniques to reduce radio communication is the dual prediction mechanism and several proposals are reported in the literature. However, while all existing approaches have been proven to be very effective in reducing the amount of data reported to the sink, their efficiency is countered by an increase in complexity. Moreover, they are very sensitive to data loss which renders the dual prediction mechanism obsolete. In the paper “*Fault Tolerant Data Transmission Reduction Technique in Wireless Sensor Networks*”, the authors present an alternative technique that has the major benefit to be simple yet robust, and more effective in terms of prediction accuracy and data reduction. Their approach exploits the fact that sensor data changes smoothly over time, therefore they leverage the prediction model proposed in to forecast future readings. They coupled this technique with a data reconstruction algorithm [15] that exploits both temporal smoothness and spatial correlation among different sensed features in order to estimate missing values (Luo et al., 2012).

Vehicular ad hoc networks (VANETs) are a subclass of mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs), and a promising approach for future intelligent transportation systems (ITS). A VANET typically supports two communication models, namely Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I). Currently, most VANET applications rely on V2V communications since they do not require costly infrastructure. However, as VANET is a very dynamic network, information must be exchanged between mobile vehicles in an efficient way by avoiding as far as possible the broadcast storm problem that occurs whenever a huge number of vehicles broadcast messages at the same time thus leading to a network saturation, packet delay, and collision issues. In this context, data aggregation is an appealing approach allowing to integration of several data about similar events to generate a summary (aka aggregate) and as a consequence potentially reduce the network traffic. There are several proposals for data aggregation in VANETs already reported in the literature. However, the highly complex urban and highway networks produce overwhelming traffic information data that requires efficient selection criteria and smart filtering before the aggregation process. The design of an efficient data aggregation approach that combines correlated traffic information or Floating Car Data (FCD) is still a challenging issue. The authors of the paper “*Towards a Smarter Directional Data Aggregation in VANETs*” introduce a new data aggregation protocol, called Smart Directional Data Aggregation (SDDA), with the goal of selecting the most appropriate FCD messages that have to be aggregated.

Based on the aforementioned research works, it is clear that the future CPSs and intelligent applications heavily rely on the presence and widespread of physical sensors and WSNs. To ensure the functionality of an application, such as intruder detection, it is of critical importance to guarantee the coverage and availability of wireless sensors during deployment. As such, barrier coverage is a critical issue for wireless sensor deployment for many industrial and military applications, where each wireless sensor can sense within its range and a collection of wireless sensors can be deployed to cover the entire range of a barrier. Over the last decade, different barrier coverage algorithms had been established for different types of sensors such as seismic and acoustic sensors, while in recent years, more research efforts are dedicated to radar sensor systems. In “*Optimal Placement of Barrier Coverage in Heterogeneous Bistatic Radar Sensor Networks*” authors investigate the barrier coverage problem for bistatic radar sensor systems. Different to the traditional passive sensing model, the Cassini oval sensing model is investigated and an optimal placement strategy for heterogeneous transmitters and receivers has been proposed to achieve maximum barrier length coverage. The proposed algorithm has been validated through theoretical simulations to demonstrate the optimal coverage (Wang et al., 2010).

Cyber-social networks have significantly improved social relationships among mobile users across device-to-device communications. In the paper “*A Detailed Review of D2D Cache in Helper Selection*”, the authors present a survey work which focuses on D2D helper selection techniques according to three basic categories, including the network frame, computing method, and social-aware attribute. Differing from other surveys which mainly consider the energy consumption and latency minimization in D2D networks, they discuss the selection of D2D helper based on different

network architectures, such as content distribution networks, peer-to-peer networks, named data networks, cellular networks, and vehicular ad-hoc networks. In particular, a variety of computing paradigms are taken into account to classify D2D helper selection techniques, such as mobile cloud computing, fog computing, and mobile edge computing.

III. REVIEW

3.1 Behavior and Influence Analytics in Social Computing

In recent years, the recommendation system has been well developed and is playing an important role across social media. In the paper “*ICFR: An Effective Incremental Collaborative Filtering based Recommendation Architecture for Personalized Websites*”, the user-based collaborative filtering algorithm is applied in an incremental recommendation implementation method, in which three important elements: user, item, and rating, are redefined, and relationships between user preferences and recommended content are utilized to improve the user-based collaborative filtering algorithm. Moreover, users’ browsing behaviors are extracted based on the analysis of Web logs from personalized websites, which can facilitate the update of users’ historical preference in the design of an incremental algorithm. Experiments demonstrate the high performance of the proposed method comparing with traditional updating methods.

Following the rapid development of mobile social networks, the paper “*From Crowdsourcing to Crowdmining: Using Implicit Human Intelligence for Better Understanding of Crowdsourced Data*” discusses the concept of crowdmining and presents a generic model for the development of crowdmining systems. The basic idea is to discover and better utilize the implicit human intelligence hidden in individual behavior patterns and crowd-object interaction patterns under a certain community context. The authors introduce a basic framework to understand the crowdsourced data with a formal description and discuss its usage in several general tasks in terms of data mining including classification, filtering and grouping. Based on these, they describe two case studies, namely the crowdevent and crowdtrip, which utilize the power of implicit human intelligence to facilitate the event sharing and trip planning respectively. Detailed scenario applications are presented, and the experiment evaluation demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method in event localization and detection, and travel route generation using online/offline crowd sourced data.

Behavioral analysis has drawn more and more attentions for mobile computing application in big data environments. In the paper “*TBI2Flow: Travel Behavioral Inertia Based Long-Term Taxi Passenger Flow Prediction*”, the authors focus on the analysis of travel patterns of taxis in cities using GPS data. Specifically, the travel behavioral inertia, which mainly includes two basic components: driver inertia and passenger inertia, is newly defined and introduced as a new metric for the long-term taxi passenger flow prediction. A traffic flow prediction framework, called TBI2Flow, is designed to forecast the distribution of taxi passengers in each small region of a district over different time intervals. The multi-layered neural network is utilized to extract and represent the new features from the taxi trajectory data based on the travel behavior analysis. The results of simulation-based experiments demonstrate the significance and efficiency of the proposed model for traffic management in the design of a smart city.

To deal with the special problem of influence maximization in social networks, the paper “*Three-hop Velocity Attenuation Propagation Model for Influence Maximization in Social Networks*” proposes a three-hop speed attenuation propagation model, based on which the authors design an algorithm for the maximum of influence considering the greedy algorithm with heuristic algorithm (Gao et al., 2014). In the constructed network model, the sum of modified degrees of the active nodes is employed to measure the impact of a node. In such a way, the influence of a single node can be effectively modeled and represented, and the lack of subtle influence caused by the three-hop simulation can be further made up. Two different datasets collected from DBLP and Facebook are used to conduct the propagation simulations, and the experiment results demonstrate the high efficiency of the proposed method comparing the traditional greedy algorithms.

IV. RESULTS

4.1 Machine Learning and Intelligent Applications

Sensors and WSNs play an important role in the CPSs and intelligent applications by offering fundamental infrastructure and data sources. However, how to process data to support decision making and provide “intelligence” in systems and applications remains a big challenge. In recent years, ML has demonstrated great potential to many

applications in consumer electronics, industrial, and security and surveillance applications. In this special issue, several unique research works are presented on various novel ML techniques and intelligent applications.

As networked systems are becoming more and more complex, automated operations and maintenance are becoming highly important to ensure efficient and reliable system operations. The paper “*Intelligent Maintenance Frameworks of Large-scale Grid using Genetic Algorithm and K-Medoids Clustering Methods*” investigates the automation and scheduling problem of maintenance of a large-scale smart grid system, where a smart grid management system (GMS) is proposed with genetic algorithm and K-medoids clustering. This research identifies and addresses different severity levels according to the faulty devices. The two proposed algorithms are validated with five real-world datasets collected in five different cities in China.

As the technologies evolved, the focus of advanced technologies also shifted to offer more intelligent and more “personalized” services to end users. This trend can be observed from consumer electronics to even manufacturing enterprises to have customized products and services. Therefore, advanced technologies for identifying the user are becoming a very important topic to ensure the delivery of safe and secure personal services. While there are various unimodal personal identification techniques such as password, facial, voice, and fingerprint, each modality exists its own weaknesses which may make the overall system vulnerable. In the paper “*An Accurate Multi-Modal Biometric Identification System for Person Identification via Fusion of Face and Finger Print*”, a multi-modal person identification approach is proposed by fusing facial and fingerprint information. The proposed method has been verified with four different datasets and has achieved a promising recognition accuracy of 99.59%.

Different to traditional artificial intelligence (or machine intelligence), research efforts are also dedicated to mimicking unique human traits, behaviors, and personalities. In addition, to offer intelligence, researchers are seeking ways to capture and represent the uniqueness of human beings in achieving human-like (or even individual-like) artifacts such as digital avatars and humanoid robots. However, there is yet a comprehensive model to systematically describe human traits and personalities. The paper “*From Effect, Behavior, and Cognition to Personality: An Integrated Personal Character Model for Individual-like Intelligent Artifacts*” offers a broad overview of the existing Personal Character Models (PCMs) from different research arenas and perspectives such as psychology and computational intelligence. A novel PCM is proposed to capture comprehensively personal affects, behaviors, cognition, and the intra- and inter-relationships between these personal characteristics. The feasibility of the proposed PCM model has been demonstrated by extracting representative personal characteristics through various personal data such as wearable devices and cognitive tests.

V. DISCUSSION

5.1 Privacy and Security in Smart Computing

One of the biggest concerns in the cyber world is security. By delegating control of physical processes to virtual entities, often accessed via wireless networks, a number of vulnerabilities arise. Without solving security issues, it is not possible to leverage the paradigms linked to the cyber physical systems. As cyber-attacks become more frequent, the research community has presented several approaches (e.g. heuristic methods) to detect and analyze malicious programs (also referred to as malware). However, designing effective and efficient malware detection approaches poses several challenges and still has open issues, for example due to counter-malware detection efforts by malware authors and cyber criminals. There are three major approaches for analyzing malware: static, dynamic and hybrid, each of them with their own pros and cons. Trying to mitigate some of the drawbacks of current static, dynamic and hybrid malware detection approaches, multi-view learning is a promising solution. Multi-view data are very common in real world applications, where data are often collected from different sources, using different measuring methods. Different data sources form different feature sets, and each set is referred to as a view. Any particular single-view data cannot comprehensively describe the phenomenon under observation. Motivated by this, multi-view learning is an emerging direction in machine learning which considers learning with multiple views to improve the generalization performance. To adapt multi-view learning for malware threat hunting, the authors of the paper “*A Multiview Learning Method for Malware Threat Hunting: Windows, IoT and Android as Case Studies*” leverage the potential of using executable files for either malware or goodware (i.e. non-malware) as the source for multi-view data extraction. The challenge they tackle in this context is to determine what algorithm can be used to effectively extract features from executable files.

Existing approaches generally use single view information for malware detection or a combination of some views in the form of a single view. In their paper, the authors propose an efficient ensemble multi-view learning method, which automatically assigns optimized weights to different views. The proposed method is a large margin classifier that improves generalization using a global optimum hypothesis. To demonstrate adaptability of the proposed approach in detecting malware on different platforms, they evaluate their system with datasets comprising Internet of Things (IoT), Windows and Android malware.

VI. CONCLUSION

This special issue aims to promote the development of cyber-related information and communication technologies in smart computing. In Particular, a variety of important topics are addressed in this special issue, including: Knowledge Modeling and Management for Cyberization, Information Sharing and Dissemination in Smart Computing, Smart Control and Monitoring for Cyberization, Cognitive Physical-Social Networks, Content Analysis and Mining in Cyber-Social Networks, Behavioral Analytics across Smart Networks, Deep Learning in Cyberization, Resource Management in heterogeneous Networks, Intelligent Transportation Systems Using Smart Networks, Smart Internet of Things, Cyber-Physical-Social Data Processing and Intelligence Mining, Smart Data Streaming and Real-Time Processing, Smart Sensors and Ad-Hoc Wireless Networks, Data Storage and Integration in Cyberspace, Semantic Web Mining in Smart Computing, Infrastructure and Platform for Intelligent Network Systems, Wearable Technologies in Smart Environments, Mobile Computing with Smart Sensors, Smart Energy Management and Sustainability, Privacy and Security in Smart Computing, and etc.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The paper consists of information related to smart computing. It focuses on the following elements and values such as introduction, methodologies, privacy, security, behaviour and influence analytics in social computing, results, and discussion followed by conclusion and references. I hereby declare that all the information provided in the respected paper is authenticated, authorized, and hence reliable. I would like to thank all the viewers and readers of this paper for their precious time.

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